

The performance of leaf springs at an end or are there future potentials?

Prof. Dr. Eckehard Müller
Bochum University of Applied Science
Lennershofstr. 140, 44801 Bochum, Germany

[References neue formatieren \[1\]](#)

Steinbeis-Transfercenter for spring technologies, component behavior and process
Langerfeldstr. 53 c, 58638 Iserlohn, Germany

Abstract:

It is always the demand to reduce the weight of cars or improving the lifetime of vehicle parts. Therefore, continuous improvement is always made. But the production costs should not rise significantly. The actual situation for parabolic leaf springs is investigated, and the possibilities are checked. It will be shown that all options with traditional material and production equipment is at an end.

Keywords: leaf spring, parabolic spring, performance, weight reduction, stress peening, durability

1. Introduction

Parabolic leaf springs are today a normal component, especially in light trucks. The demand is always to reduce weight. In the last years, weight reduction has been achieved. But at the moment strong efforts must be done to improve the durability without increasing the costs. In this paper, possibilities will be presented to get a further weight reduction

2. Basics

Leaf springs have been used for hundreds of years in vehicles. One of the first applications is the suspension of coaches. The development continues, and the first cars had leaf springs. In further decades, the spring was more and more optimized.

The basic idea is that a beam in bending is used in the elastic range to compensate bumpinesses of the road. If the stress distribution is seen along the beam (starting in the middle) is linear decreasing (beam in bending). This situation is very unsatisfied because in the end the material is not utilized about the stress. The first attempt to compensate this fact to use several leaves to get a more uniform distribution.

Fig. 2-1: schematic distribution of the stresses

A typical old-fashioned leaf spring is shown in the following figure:

Fig. 2-2: conventional leaf spring with 11 leaves (figure SOGEFI)

Especially in heavily loaded trucks, this solution is still implemented because of the rough environment. If one leaf will break, no total loss of the spring is given.

Looking at the weight compared with the rate of the spring respectively, the stress the material is not at the limit. The idea is to get a uniform distribution along with the leaf. The consequence is a thickness of the arm like a parable or better as a mathematical root-function. In the middle, it is thick, and in the end, it is thin. This kind of spring is called a parabolic leaf spring. To compare a conventional spring with a parabolic leaf spring the number of leaves can be reduced from more than 10 to 3 leaves.

Fig. 2-3: three leaf parabolic leaf spring (courtesy of SOGEFI)

The leave of a parabolic leaf spring is normally achieved by rolling every side three times. After rolling the leaf is quenched to get a martensitic structure. Afterwards it is tempered to get the right tensile strength. (see next chapter)

3. Production

The tensile strength R_m of the springs increases during the time from $R_m = 1500$ MPa to 1750 MPa. The next step to shot peen the leaf. For parabolic spring, the peening will be done under a prestress to increase the induced compressive residual stresses. Afterward, the spring is going to be painted. These are the main steps to get an overview. In the following chapter, the steps where a potential seemed to be, will be explained.

3.1. Principle production process

The different production steps are described in the following paragraphs. There are some more steps necessary compared to conventional leaf springs [FI 87a].

Fig. 3-1: different steps of production a parabolic leaf spring

3.1 Different production steps

Starting in the raw material. It is mostly 50 Cr V 4 delivered in bars. For thinner leaves also 55 Cr 3. Nearly every bar has already decarburization at the surface up to 150 μm . Nobody (in the world) delivers non decarburized material. Grinding the bars is a solution but is expensive.

Now the bar is cut to the right length and afterwards heated up every side separately. After reaching the temperatures each end is rolled to the necessary shape of thickness. In the next step, the leaf is heated in a furnace up to 900° C for quenching in oil. Afterwards it is tempered to get the right tensile strength. This point or step gave a possibility to increase the performance of the spring or reducing the weight. But the tensile strength is at 1750 MPa at the limit. A higher strength would reduce ductability drastically. At this point, the limit with these materials is reached. One step could be to use Silicon steels. This steel is more expensive and at the moment nobody in the automotive industry will pay more for leaf springs.

The next step after quenching is the so-called setting or plastification. The spring is loaded that the stress is over the tensile strength. The consequence is a plastification zone starting at the surface into deep zones. It can be more than 1 mm. [Mu 02] The setting is done to get compressive residual stresses in deeper regions to increase the durability. The second advantage is the reduction of the relaxation of the spring. A leaf spring in a car/truck is permanently under load caused by the weight of the vehicle. During the time is a loss of the spring rate which lowers the vehicle. This could be up to 9 %. With his step, an artificial aging process is performed, and the relaxation is reduced under 3 % [Fi 87b].

The next step is stress peening [MU 19]. Conventional leaf spring is normal peened, because it makes no sense to stress peen them. The spring is loaded up to 10 % to 20 % under the tensile strength to get high tensile stress in the spring. It is fixed in a special mounting device. Now it will be peened and afterwards unloaded. The induced compressive residual stress increases in the amount and depth. In the next step, the painting is done with different options. One option is a zinc-rich primer or high sophisticated surface coating.

If the spring consists of some leaves the spring is assembled. Also, at this step, the bushings are pressed into the eyes. Another setting follows to adjust the exact arc height because the spring is not straight (see fig. 3-2). After inspection, the spring is complete to be assembled in a truck/car.

A very new development of a one leaf parabolic spring for light trucks is shown in the following figure:

Fig: 3-2: result of recent development of light weighted parabolic leaf spring (courtesy of SOGEFI)

For special applications, fiber-reinforced springs are used. They are very light-weighted but expensive. Another aspect is the recycling of these kinds of springs. They can only be shredded.

Another development is air springs, which were mainly used in trucks. For assembling so-called airlinks were used which are special parabolic springs. Airlinks are manufactured in principle in the same way.

3.2 Special Aspects

The basic question is always what can be done to increase the performance? This means, on the other side to reduce the weight at the same fatigue parameters.

One question which always arises is to go nearer to the production limits. The consequence is to reduce the tolerances concerning all parameters in the process. Looking at the production, process it looks like normal, not a highly sophisticated process. There are many parameters to be controlled in such a way, which increases production costs. The demand for low prices forbite more efforts in this direction.

The carburization of the raw material during the production may increase up to 500 μm . This additional decarburization occurs in the furnace for heating the raw material up to around 900 °C. The time in the furnace is about 20 min. The demand for better raw material is senseless because producing spring steel is a niche business and costs are very high.

One possibility might be to change the peening process. One main parameter is peening time. This can be done at low costs.

4. Investigation of the shot peening performance

One question to get an answer is if doubling the peening time gives higher residual stress, which causes better durability. Before reporting about the experiment, the basics of stress peening will be explained now.

4.1 Basics concerning stress peening

Stress peening is a further development of the normal peening process. A typical residual stress profile of normal shot peening has the maximum of compressive residual stress for steel with a high hardness under the surface. [MU 06, SC 06]

Fig 4-1: typical residual stress profile for spring steel with decarburized surface

The maximum of the compressive residual stress depends on the shot diameter. The greater the diameter the deeper the maximum. In reality, it is much less compressive residual stress because the surface is decarburized, and the profile is distorted because the impact energy is distributed in the material in slide different way.

Stress Peening means that the surface of the spring is peened under high tensile stress. After peening, the spring is unloaded, and the compressive residual stress rises. The main reason why stress peening works is the fact that it is always the same residual stress profile for different tensile stresses before. [MU 92, MU 99] This means that you always reach the same stress level, but more prestress gives a deeper compressive residual stress profile. The maximum compressive residual stress level is limited to $(71 \pm 6) \%$ of the tensile strength of the material [HI 15]. The characteristics of the different stress levels during the whole process is shown in figure 4-2.

Because the bending stress is along with the leaf, you get only stress peened residual stress profile also along with the leaf. Perpendicular to the leaf you get conventional residual stress profiles.

Fig. 4-2: Schematic residual stress distribution during the stress peening process

4.2 Experimental investigation

Two different materials for leaf springs were investigated to get information about the effect of peening the double time. One type is standard spring steel 51 Cr V 4 and is enhanced material which has a reduction of 40 % sulfur and phosphor compared to the batch of the standard material.

Samples were cut out of a parabolic leaf spring. Afterwards, they ground to get a non-decarburized surface to see also the effects of shot peening near the surface. They were 10 cm to 10 cm and at least 20 mm high. The samples were not stress peened, because the normal residual stress distribution is more sensitive for differences between the two mentioned materials.

The peening was done under normal conditions, which were used to the normal manufacturing process.

Also, two whole leaves out of standard spring steel were peened under stress as under production conditions. One leaf was peened twice. Here is the aim to see the residual stress profile under production conditions. The material was taken of a normally delivered lot.

The residual stress was determined by x-ray diffraction using the $\cos\alpha$ -method. Theory can be read e. g. in [RA 16, SA 14] and for practical applications [MU 17]. The equipment which was used was a pulstec μ -360s. The x-ray spot has a 4 mm diameter. The material to get a depth profile was electrolytically removed. The errors of the measurements are 7 %.

5. Results

The always ask question or demand is extending the peening time more residual stresses can be induced. The answer is given for both materials in figure 5-1. The other question is if you can induce more residual stresses in springs out of enhanced material. Also, this answer is given in this figure.

Fig. 5-1: Residual stress result by normal peening

If you compare the blue line with the red line (normal material), there is no difference. Comparing gray with yellow (enhanced material) is also a significant difference. The point (yellow line) at 425 μm can be interpreted as a statistical measuring error and is not significant. The conclusion is that peening longer gives no difference and from the economic view the peening used up to now is at an optimum. (Shorter peening time does not show enough coverage.) Comparing now blue with gray and red with yellow there also is no difference. The conclusion here is that the enhanced material makes no difference. Another question is this context is:

What is the increase in stress peening?

One leaf is stress peened under normal production conditions, the second one is peened twice as long. Theoretical a constant compressive residual stress should be first 100 μm to 200 μm like shown in figure 4-2. The reality is different (see figure 5-2). For this increase, the compressive residual stress decarburization is responsible. In this zone is less tensile strength R_m of the material and the limit of the maximum residual stress is less. If you see the values at 50 μm depth, it is around -850 MPa. This means a tensile strength of around 1200 MPa to 1250 MPa. At the blue curve is a plateau between 150 μm to 250 μm depth. The residual stress values are nearly constant around -1100 MPa, which gives a $R_m = 1650$ MPa. The red curve shows decarburization up to 200 μm. Because of the less energy used up to this depth, the residual stress profile goes deeper, but the cracks start at the surface and there the highness of the compressive residual stress is very important.

Fig 5-2: Residual stress profiles induced by stress peening

The question of the higher tensile strength of the material is also limited. Approximately at $R_m = 1800$ MPa at the material tempered martensite embrittlement (TME) begins, which drastically gives less ductility, and supports a higher crack initiation and velocity.

6. Conclusion

The final conclusions can be resumed in one sentence. An improvement of parabolic leaf springs concerning durability respectively weight cannot be done with the existing production possibilities.

Looking at coil springs an increase of the tensile strength of the material to reduce the weight of the spring can only be done with new row material like silicon steel [DZ 19]. This causes higher costs concerning material and production.

Acknowledgement

These results are obtained within the project LIGHTTECH (GA-No. 799787), which is supported by the Research Fund Coal and Steel. We thank for the financial support.

References

- DZ 19 Dziemballa, H.: Schraubendruckfedern. In Müller, E u. Hermann, W. (Hrsg.): Fahrzeugfedern 2019, Steinbeis-Transferzentrum für Federntechnologie, Bauteilverhalten und Prozeß, Iserlohn, 2019, pp. 59-89
- FI 87a Fischer, F.; Vondracek, H.: Warmgeformte Federn, Hoesch Hohenlimburg AG, Hagen, 1987, p. 177
- FI 87b Fischer, F.; Vondracek, H.: Warmgeformte Federn, Hoesch Hohenlimburg AG, Hagen, 1987, p. 224
- HI 15 Hilairi, N. K. J.: Untersuchung der maximale Druckeigenspannung in Federelementen im Vergleich zur Zugfestigkeit, Bachelor-Arbeit, Hochschule Bochum, Labor für Feinstrukturanalyse (Prof. Dr. E. Müller), 2015
- MU 02 Müller, E; Terbille S.: Simulation und Messung von Eigenspannungen nach dem Setzen von Parabelfedern, VDI-Berichte 1757, VDI-Verlag, Düsseldorf, 2003, p. 27
- MU 06 E. Müller, E: Optimization of Shot Peening for Fatigue Critical Applications, in S. Baiker (Edt.): Shot Peening, Metall Finishing News, Wetzikon, 2006, pp. 120 -127
- MU 17 Müller, E.: Röntgenografische Eigenspannungsmessungen -Vergleich zweier Methoden-. In H. Frenzen, J. Lange (Hrsg.): Fortschritte in der Werkstoffprüfung für Forschung und Praxis, Deutscher Verband für Materialforschung und -prüfung e. V., 2017, pp. 147-150

- MU 19 Mueller, E: Stress Peening—A Sophisticated Way of Normal Shot Peening. *Journal of Materials Science and Engineering A & Journal of Materials Science and Engineering B*, Volume 9 (2019), Number 2, pp. 56 - 63
- MU 92 Müller, E.: Der Einfluß des Plastizierens und des Kugelstrahlens auf die Ausbildung von Eigenspannungen in Blattfedern; *Berichte aus Forschung und Entwicklung* 1/92 (1992), Hoesch AG, Dortmund, pp. 23 - 29
- MU 99 E. Müller, E.: The Development of Residual Stress at Bending Specimens under the Influence of Setting and Stress Peening, in Nakonieczny, A. (Ed.): *Proceedings of the 7th international conference of shot peening*, Institute of Precision Mechanics, Warsaw, 1999, p. 88
- RA 16 Ramirez-Rico, J., Lee, S.-Y., Ling J. J, Noyan, I. C.: Stress measurement using area detectors. A theoretical and experimental comparison of different methods in ferritic steel using a portable X-ray apparatus. *Journal of Materials Science* 51 (2016), pp. 5343–5355
- SA 14 Sasaki, T.: New Generation X-Ray Stress Measurement Using Debye Ring Image Data by Two-Dimensional Detection. *Materials Science Forum* Vol. 783-786 (2014), pp 2103-2108
- SC 06 Schulze, V.: *Modern Mechanical Surface Treatment*, Wiley-VCH Verlag, Weinheim, 2006, p. 54